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**COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON THE ECONOMIC
LANDSCAPE OF SOCIETY**

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Abstract: *Artificial intelligence is associated with the fact that scientists are trying to create a certain subject area that includes the representation itself, the image of human knowledge about the world. And here the research of artificial intelligence comes to the fore. This article examines the role of artificial intelligence in society and human life and its impact on the development of mankind and various sectors of the economy. Forecasts of the impact of the use of artificial intelligence in the future period are also given.*

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INTRODUCTION

Natural intelligence is a set of human abilities, firstly, to distinguish something essential in the available data of experience and knowledge, secondly, the ability to set goals and select knowledge, thirdly, the ability to reason, fourthly, the ability to evaluate knowledge and actions, fifthly, the ability to create "sixth, the ability to build an action in a rapidly changing life situation.

Artificial intelligence, in this regard, will connect with the choice of programs, for example, chess programs.

Another aspect of artificial intelligence research is related to the fact that scientists are trying to create a certain subject area that includes the representation itself, the image of human knowledge about the world. And here the research of artificial intelligence comes to the fore.

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Modern society is unable to imagine its life without gadgets and the Internet. It is worth noting the great role of these gadgets in the development and comfort of mankind, you can endlessly list how much it became easier to live after their appearance. For example, it is easy to store photos from five or ten years ago in one phone or cloud storage, and it is also convenient to communicate with friends abroad without significant costs, by sending photos and videos. Students no longer need to carry heavy books or stand in long queues when paying for utilities. Humanity is so attached to their smartphones that if the battery runs out, there is a feeling that a person is lost in the middle of the desert. It is worth noting that humanity has moved to a new level of digitalization, where there are not only technologies next to us, but also an assistant with whom we can communicate, ask questions, control what is happening, and much more.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The problem of the formation of artificial intelligence is connected with the study of human consciousness in Modern and Modern times. These are the works of R. Descartes, I. Kant, G.V. Leibniz, B. Spinoza, D. Hume, G. Rickert. The split into "spiritual" and "material" was reflected at the beginning of the XX century in the writings of E. Husserl [1].

In the works of M.D. Kuparashvili[2], the specificity of the birth of mental activity is investigated. This author pays attention to the very mechanism of the formation of qualitatively new knowledge. In the works of A.D. Moskovchenko[3], the idea of the intensification of knowledge about natural and artificial technologies is investigated. Artificial intelligence turns out to be connected in his works with the "autotrophic" lifestyle of a person, with planetary production, and with the transition to ultra-efficient technologies.

In the works of V.A. Rybin, a unified science of man is being developed, and a critical rethinking of the concept of information in cybernetics is given.

In the works of Nazirov A.E., the levels of the foundations of intellectual knowledge are investigated, and the mechanisms of self-organization in the formation of natural science theories are revealed[4].

In the works of D.I. Dubrovsky, an informational approach to the problem of consciousness and the brain is being developed.

The philosophical problems of computerization are analyzed in the works of M. Yu. Openkov. In this regard, the "virtual reality" itself is described by an ontological and, at the same time, a dialogical approach. M.Yu. Openkov explores the creativity of the very idea of a "place" in cyberspace. His works analyze human intelligence in the context of the philosophy of social networks. His works on the philosophy of intelligence are of great importance for the management of knowledge itself[5].

Artificial intelligence in this regard correlates with cognitive reflection, which acts as a moment of a more meaningful cultural whole. In the works of A.F. Kudryashev, O.I. Elkhovoy's problem of intelligence is developed following the

"modality of desire". This important problem for ontology and epistemology is associated with the study of the concept of "virtual reality". In the works of M.I. Bilalov, a hypothesis is put forward about the nonverbal, to the verbal form of truth, about the functionality of its criterion, which contributes to the knowledge of the cultural component of artificial intelligence. However, despite the sufficient elaboration of the concepts of "intelligence" and "artificial intelligence" in the literature, there is still a need to analyze the philosophical foundations of artificial intelligence itself.

Artificial intelligence as an ideal is a rather abstract construction that does not have any real objects under it. At the same time, artificial intelligence is a kind of ideal human task, but this task, in essence, is connected with mental processes. In this regard, artificial intelligence provides an enhanced synthesis of cognitive psychological procedures that have both a sensory and a rational basis.

Note that the scientist fully understands that the knowledge gained in the field of chemistry is different from the knowledge gained in the field of biology. As a result, artificial intelligence is a certain set of human abilities: to find some essential beginning in knowledge itself, to express the very possibility of reflection, to create a goal, and to choose the means to achieve it. In this regard, artificial intelligence as a kind of ideal, of course, presupposes the cognitive activity of a person, then - the ability of a person to adapt to a situation, and finally, the synthesis of cognitive procedures itself. But artificial activity, in essence, is the same natural, intellectual (scientific research) activity, only, perhaps, deprived of the very "character" of activity.

It is believed that the practice of AI began with the earliest programmable machine — an automatic player that reproduces music using water and air — which was proposed by the brothers Banu Musa, who lived in Baghdad in the IX century and used the manuscripts of ancient Greek thinkers in their work[6].

In the XVII century. computing machines began to appear: V. Shikkard's "counting clocks", which allowed adding using modified Napier bones, B. Pascal's "Pascaline", which was a more advanced form of an adding machine and capable of

performing both addition and subtraction operations, and G.V. Leibniz's calculator, which automated multiplication and division operations.

As the researchers suggest, Leibniz was also close to the idea of creating a universal formal language that could be used to formulate problems and solve them algorithmically, which partly contributed to the development of integral and differential calculus by the mathematician and philosopher[7].

METHODOLOGY

It is impossible to imagine how we would live without this assistant, today we can not be afraid that we do not know the city, the road to our destination, languages, professional terms, and so on. All this opens up great opportunities for humanity. Is it so? Shifting to artificial intelligence all the things that we can't or don't want to remember, does it open up great opportunities for us? We'll figure it out.

We surveyed different categories of people: students, working class, and pensioners. To determine how much artificial intelligence we use in everyday life and in what areas.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research results show that artificial intelligence has become so integrated into our lives that we don't even notice that we use it.

How often do you interact with artificial intelligence-based technologies?

Figure No. 1. Usage of Artificial Intelligence

The results show that most people do not even know that they use artificial intelligence in everyday life, but they think that it is a program that can be used in special cases. Many people have a lot of technologies running on artificial intelligence, but they don't even know that it is artificial intelligence.

Figure No. 2. Areas of activity where artificial intelligence should not be used.

The survey asked questions about artificial intelligence. From the data obtained, Figure No. 2, we learned that healthcare and education should exist without the use of artificial intelligence (42% of people believe that artificial intelligence should not be used in healthcare, 38% believe that it should not be used in education). It is worth noting that in the process of studying, the modern young generation carries out together with artificial intelligence, whether it is information collection, analysis, translation, search, and so on. Such a picture has puzzled us very much that this is becoming a complex controlled process. In addition, you need to pay attention to the fact that even schoolchildren can use artificial intelligence.

Figure No. 3. Expectations from the further development of AI.

Also, according to the survey, it can be seen that the further development of artificial intelligence (Figure No. 3), according to the respondents, will help solve most problems (58%) and at the same time contribute to a decrease in the intelligence of mankind (54%). Naturally, AI will help many people, especially people with disabilities, people with health problems, foreigners, the elderly, and many others. However, there is a problem that this AI is used mainly among young people to do homework and find answers to tests.

If we do not react to this process now, then the next generation will be divided into two groups of people, people who create artificial intelligence (intellectuals) and the second category of people who are completely dependent on artificial intelligence. Just imagine you are in a foreign country and absolutely do not know the area, and suddenly all your gadgets are turned off and you are lost, it's sad that you did not remember the way because you were hoping for a navigator, but you can't call a friend because you also did not bother to remember the phone number.

CONCLUSION

Artificial intelligence is already an integral part of our lives, and our lives are increasingly entangled with it. Sometimes it seems that artificial intelligence knows more about us than we do. And we will soon follow everything that the AI tells us. The existence of artificial intelligence calms and increases confidence while traveling, filling out documents, and much more. However, it is worth considering that the younger generation fully uses and fully trusts AI. We believe that this can lead to the fact that we begin to degrade and not use our brains to remember ordinary things. Therefore, it is worth monitoring the use of AI in different areas. In our opinion, its best application will be in the field of tourism, testing, and consulting when collecting analyses in healthcare.

REFERENCES

1. Descartes R. Works. 1989. - 654 p.; Kant I. Critique of Pure Reason. - Simferopol, 1998. - 528 p.; Leibniz G.V.T. Works in 4 volumes: Vol. 4. - Moscow: Mysl, 1989. - 554 p.; Spinoza B.
2. Husserl E. Logical Investigations. Prolegomena to Pure Logic. Vol. 1. - St. Petersburg, 1909. - 224 p.
3. Moskovchenko A.D. Philosophy of autotrophic civilization. The problem of integration of humanitarian, natural and technical sciences. - M., 2007-2010.
4. Nazirov A.E. Development of science and scientific and technological progress. - St. Petersburg, 2012.
5. Openkov M.Yu. Creativity of Place // Ecology of Culture. - Arkhangelsk. - No. 2; Philosophy of Social Networks: Communication of Knowledge // Communication on the Internet: Good or Evil. - Arkhangelsk, 2014. In co-authorship; Ontology of Mobility // Philosophical Problems of Information Technology and Cyberspace. - Pyatigorsk, 2014; Ontology and Theory of Knowledge. - Arkhangelsk, 2013. In co-authorship.

6. Koetsier, T. On the prehistory of programmable machines: musical automata, looms, calculators / T. Koetsier. — Text : independent // Theory of mechanisms and machines. - 2001. - vol. 36. - No. 5. — p. 590.

7. Gaidenko, P.P. The formation of New European Natural science: overcoming the paradoxes of the actually infinite / P.P. Gaidenko. — Text : direct // Metaphysics. — 2011.